

EFFECT OF IMPURITIES ON THE ENHANCED CATALYTIC ACTIVITY FOR HYDROGEN EVOLUTION IN HIGH PURITY MAGNESIUM

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Abstract

The accumulation of impurities more noble than magnesium (Mg) during dissolution has been suggested to be responsible for the enhanced catalytic activity of hydrogen evolution reaction on anodically polarized Mg surfaces. The effect of impurities on the so-called Negative Difference Effect was studied by galvanostatic experiments coupled with simultaneous measurements of H₂ gas collection on electrodes of high purity (99.98% Mg) and ultra-high purity Mg (99.9999% Mg). The concentration of impurities was shown to have a strong effect on the anodic hydrogen evolution (HE), as the HE rates decreased with increasing purity of the Mg. However, HE rates were very large for both Mg electrodes when they were subjected to anodic polarization. These observations demonstrate that, even though the concentration of impurities influences anodic HE on dissolving Mg surfaces, this phenomenon cannot be fully explained in terms of impurity enrichment. The effects of Fe enrichment and the corrosion product film are shown to play a small role in the enhanced HE rates during anodic polarization. The large enhancement of HE rate during anodic dissolution was instead shown to be associated with hydrogen evolved at the regions of anodic dissolution.

Key Words: Magnesium; hydrogen evolution; anodic dissolution; cathodic reaction; NDE.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Magnesium (Mg) alloys are materials of technological interest that are suitable for many different applications because of their weight and mechanical properties [1]. However, their high corrosion rates have limited their use. Improving the understanding of the basic principles of Mg corrosion represents the first step to explain and, eventually, improve the corrosion behavior of Mg alloys.

It is well known that the hydrogen evolution (HE) accompanies Mg dissolution under open circuit conditions [1]. Mg and its alloys exhibit very low corrosion potentials (E_{corr}) that are far below the reversible potential (E_{rev}) for the HE reaction (HER). The half reactions associated with the reduction of protons (H^+) and water (H_2O) in acidic and neutral/alkaline environments, respectively, produce copious HE at these low potentials. The open circuit reactions can therefore be described by [1]:

where Eq. (1) is the anodic half reaction, and Eq. (2) and (3) are the cathodic half reactions in acidic and in neutral/alkaline media, respectively, and Eq. (4) is the overall reaction.

When Mg and its alloys are forced to dissolve at anodic potentials, an increase in the HE rate is observed, which has been termed the Negative Difference Effect (NDE) [1, 2]. According to the well-accepted expression for activation-controlled electrochemical reactions, the Butler–Volmer equation, the rate of a cathodic reaction such as the HER (Eq. (2) and (3)) should decrease exponentially and not increase with increasing anodic polarization. The NDE is defined by the

difference between the HE rate on an electrode at the E_{corr} and during anodic polarization. Because the HE rate increases with increasing anodic potential in the case of Mg and its alloys, this difference is a negative number. The NDE, or anodic HE, has been reported for other metals such as lithium (Li) [3] and aluminum (Al) [4, 5].

Different mechanistic explanations for the NDE have been made since it was first reported by Beetz in 1866 [6]. The most popular in the last decades is based on the hypothetical existence of Mg^+ as an intermediate in the anodic dissolution of Mg. The univalent Mg theory, initially invoked by Petty et al. [7], has been promoted by Song and Atrens [8-12]. In this theory, Mg and its alloys undergo a two-step dissolution mechanism in which an electrochemical reaction that first produces Mg^+ is followed by a chemical reaction of Mg^+ with water to form Mg^{2+} and H_2 :

According to this mechanism, an increase in the dissolution rate of Mg, which occurs at higher applied potentials, would lead to an increase in the HE rate. While this theory can explain the increase in HE rate with increasing applied current or potential, the existence of Mg^+ has never been detected by any experimental technique. In fact, it has recently been shown that the most referenced evidence for the existence of Mg^+ can be rationalized by alternative explanations [13].

Recent reports by Atrens and coworkers have suggested that the average oxidation number, n , at open circuit can be less than 1 in some cases, and even as low as 0.06 [14]. To explain this observation, the authors hypothesized that pits or defective regions in the Mg oxide film were sealed off by hydrogen bubbles to form crevices separated from the bulk environment. However, even if such blockage occurred, spherical bubbles could only block circular openings that were widely separated, which does not describe the roughness observed on dissolving Mg surfaces. The

measurement of such low apparent values of n only highlights the difficulties in using gravimetric and electrochemical methods for the accurate determination of n .

With similar motivation, Lebouil et al. [15] studied the kinetics of HER on pure Mg as a function of time by means of time resolved volumetry in connection with an atomic emission spectroelectrochemistry (AESEC) electrochemical flow cell. A steady rate of Mg dissolution was observed correlating with the electrochemical current for an $n=2$ dissolution mechanism. Rossrucker et al. [16] studied the dissolution of pure magnesium using an electrochemical flow cell combined with an inductively coupled plasma–mass spectrometer (ICP-MS). This method allowed the quantification of Mg dissolution during anodic and cathodic polarization and revealed that Mg dissolves with a stoichiometry of $n=2$. In a very recent work, Cain et al. [17] studied Mg dissolution mechanism by means of combined electrochemical and weight loss measurements. The net charge associated with hydrogen evolution plus the net charge measured by the potentiostat during anodic polarization were compared to mass loss as a function of different applied anodic potentials. Robust evidence that pure Mg dissolved via Mg^{2+} were reported. These experimental findings oppose the univalent Mg dissolution mechanism and suggest that neither the open circuit corrosion mechanism of Mg nor the anodic HE occur via this species.

An alternative explanation for the HE upon anodic polarization has been proposed in which the catalytic activity of the surface increases with increasing applied potential or current as embodied by increases in the exchange current density for the HE reaction on Mg ($i_{0,H_2,Mg}$) [18]. In this model, $i_{0,H_2,Mg}$ is viewed not as a constant, but rather as a dynamic parameter that changes due to anodic polarization in a way that reflects the enhanced catalytic activity of the Mg surface for the HE reaction.

This change in the catalytic activity would be affected by the formation of an oxide film as well as the nature of the oxide film such as composition or coverage. When Mg dissolves at the OCP, dark regions progressively appear on the initially silvery surface, eventually covering it completely. Several authors have observed the appearance of these local dark regions, which propagate at a higher rate when Mg is forced to dissolve at anodic potentials [19-21]. Curioni [19] reported that during cathodic polarization of pure Mg in 3.5 wt.% NaCl solution, the propagation rate of the dark regions was significantly slower than at OCP conditions, confirming that the occurrence of this darkening was mainly induced by the anodic reaction. Williams et al. [21] studied the behavior of anodically polarized high purity Mg electrodes in 2 M NaCl solution by means of scanning vibrating electrode technique (SVET). Dark points were observed on the surface at the initial stages of polarization, and these were revealed to be intense local anodes. The local darkening propagated in filiform-like tracks coupled with movement of the local anodes at their leading edges. Interestingly, as the dark points moved away from their initial location, the dark filiform-like tracks left behind exhibited a strong cathodic activation. Furthermore, H₂ was reported to evolve near or at their leading edges. Birbilis et al. [20] also reported the filiform-like morphology of the darkened regions formed on high purity Mg subjected to anodic dissolution, confirming that that oxidation of Mg during anodic polarization is not uniform. In summary, the corroded dark regions and the rate at which they propagate along the surface have been suggested to be primarily responsible for the enhanced catalytic activity for HER of dissolving Mg surfaces. Nevertheless, its role in the process as well as other factors that might contribute the occurrence of this phenomenon are still not clear.

During Mg dissolution, the impurities present in the bulk material have been reported to accumulate in the dark film formed on the surface in higher concentrations than in the bulk metal

[22]. Owing to the active potential of Mg, almost any trace element present in the metal is likely to be noble and enrich on the surface or in surface films as Mg is preferentially dissolved. HE would occur readily on the sites of enriched noble elements even at potentials for which Mg is anodically polarized owing to the high i_{0,H_2} expected for those elements, thereby contributing to the enhanced catalytic activity for HER of dissolving Mg surfaces. The exact role of enriched impurities has not been fully determined and therefore remains a topic of interest. McNulty and Hanawalt [23] studied the corrosion behavior of different high purity Mg alloys by means of anodic polarization and H₂ collection. They reported corrosion rates that were initially high and then decreased within the first 24 h of experimentation. This was explained by the exposure on the electrode surface of impurities more noble than Mg, which sustained the cathodic reaction even though an oxide film formed on the metal surface upon immersion into the electrolyte. The decrease in the corrosion rate was associated with the formation of a denser oxide film that would partially block the local cathodes. In a recent work, Taheri et al. [22] studied cross-sections of corroded surfaces of pure Mg by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The film was found to consist of an outer columnar mixed magnesium oxide-hydroxide layer on top of a magnesium oxide-rich inner layer. X-ray energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) revealed very small Fe-rich particles embedded in the columnar outer layer. They proposed that these Fe particles in the oxide could be responsible for the enhanced catalytic activity of Mg surfaces during dissolution. According to this, an increase in the amount of Fe might result in increasing HE rates. A very recent work used Rutherford Backscattering Spectrometry (RBS) to evaluate the enrichment of Fe in Mg previously subjected to anodic polarization. RBS was able to provide clear evidence of Fe enrichment on the electrode surface, under the surface corrosion film [17].

In other recent work, Samaniego et al. [24] studied the influence of noble element enrichment on the rate of HE for three different Mg alloys containing high concentrations of Li, Ca or Fe and compared the behavior to high purity Mg. All three alloys exhibited a strong NDE. The HE rates on the Mg-Li alloy and pure Mg were similar and smaller than those on the Mg-Ca and Mg-Fe alloys. Changes in surface alloy composition resulting from selective dissolution were not measured, but the authors assumed that Fe would enrich on the surface whereas Li and Ca would preferentially dissolve. The observation of similar rates of anodic hydrogen for an alloy that should enrich in a noble element (Mg-Fe) and one that should be depleted of a more-active element (Mg-Ca) indicates that noble element enrichment is not the only factor explaining the nature of anodic HE.

The aim of the present paper is to study the influence of low levels of impurities on the HE occurring under anodic polarizations. For that purpose, two Mg electrodes with different concentration of impurities are investigated by measuring the rate of HE during the application of anodic and cathodic constant charge at different current densities. The effects of corrosion film formation, the volume of H₂ evolved during anodic polarization and the effect on the cathodic kinetics of prior galvanostatic treatment are also discussed.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two electrodes of high purity and ultra-high purity Mg (referred to for simplicity as HP and UHP, respectively), were used as test specimens. The HP Mg used in this work¹ was the same material tested in previous works [18, 24], while the UHP Mg was obtained from United Mineral and Chemical Corporation (NJ, USA). Table 1 shows the chemical composition of the two

¹ HP Mg sample was provided by N. Birbilis

materials according to ICP–AES analysis and to the manufacturer for the HP and UHP Mg, respectively. It is worth noting that the concentration of Fe was 40 ppm and 0.1 ppm for the HP and the UHP Mg specimens, respectively. Samples were cold mounted in epoxy resin and a series of silicon carbide papers were used to grind the samples to a 1200 grit finish under ethanol prior to testing. The electrical connection was carried out by attaching a copper wire to the rear part of the metal prior to mounting. The exposed surface area was about 1.19 and 0.79 cm² for the HP and UHP Mg, respectively. The test solution was 0.1 M NaCl (pH~6). All solutions were prepared from laboratory grade reagents and with high purity water of 18.2 MΩ cm (Millipore™ system).

A conventional three-electrode configuration was used, with the sample acting as working electrode, a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode and a platinum mesh as counter electrode. All the potentials presented in the present study are thus referred to the SCE. The test assembly, described elsewhere [18], allowed simultaneous application of a galvanostatic signal along with a real-time H₂ collection. A total net charge of 20 C was passed at different applied anodic and cathodic current densities over the range of –75 to + 75 mA/cm². The open circuit potential (OCP) of the samples was monitored for 10 and 15 minutes for the HP and UHP, respectively, prior to the application of the galvanostatic signals. This was the time needed to reach a stable potential.

Cathodic potentiodynamic polarization curves were carried out immediately after the galvanostatic treatment. For these experiments the electrolyte was replaced by fresh 0.1 M NaCl solution and the cathodic polarization measurement was performed scanning downwards 700 mV from the OCP. A potential scan rate of 1 mV/s was used.

A Gamry Instruments Reference 600 potentiostat/galvanostat controlled by the Gamry Framework software was used to perform the electrochemical experiments.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Potentiodynamic polarization

Fig. 1 shows the potentiodynamic polarization response of the HP and UHP Mg in 0.1 M NaCl solution. These experiments were carried out in a quiescent electrolyte and in a single upward scan. Since Mg dissolution has been reported to occur even at low cathodic overpotentials [16], the potential sweep was performed starting in the cathodic region to minimize surface dissolution. The results of triplicate experiments are plotted, showing very good reproducibility. Significant differences were observed between the two materials. The HP Mg showed an E_{corr} of about $-1.6 V_{\text{SCE}}$ and no sign of passivity, while the UHP exhibited a less noble E_{corr} of about $-1.8 V_{\text{SCE}}$, and a slight passive-like region of around 100 mV before the typical ideally non-polarizable electrode behavior observed for the HP Mg. Another interesting difference is observed in the cathodic response of both materials. No visual sign of attack was observed on the electrode surface during the short period at the OCP. However, the cathodic current density was significantly lower for the UHP Mg than for the HP Mg, indicating a lower catalytic activity of its surface for the HER. Given the composition of the UHP Mg, it is expected that less impurity would be present on the surface during the initial cathodic polarization. This observation therefore supports the concept that the catalytic activity for HE is dependent on surface impurities and confirms that, in the absence of any corrosion film formed on the surface, they play a large role in the cathodic kinetics. It should be noted that this decreased rate of HE was responsible for the lower E_{corr} and the ability to observe the passive like behavior in a potential region that is dominated by the cathodic reaction for the HP Mg.

3.2. Galvanostatic experiments and H₂ collection

Figs. 2 and 3 show the volume of H₂ collected during the application of different current densities as a function of time in 0.1 M NaCl solution for the HP and the UHP Mg electrodes, respectively. The HE rate was linear in all cases, although an initiation time or period of lower rate was observed for current densities at and near zero. Hydrogen gas is very soluble in aqueous environments [15, 25] so it is likely that some H₂ was lost by dissolution in the first stages of experimentation. The steady state HE rates were determined from the linear portion of the curves and are plotted in Fig. 4 for the HP and UHP Mg as a function of the applied current density. The results of duplicate experiments are plotted; HE rates that appear as a single point in the plot correspond to overlapped values due the high reproducibility observed. The behavior in Fig. 4 is very similar to that previously reported for pure Mg [18], with HE rates that decreased with decreasing applied cathodic current density until reaching a minimum at the OCP. The HE rate then increased with increasing applied anodic current density. The rate of HE was greater for a given cathodic current density than for an anodic current density of the same magnitude. The results from the HP and UHP Mg were very similar in the cathodic region, which is expected since the rate of HE should depend only on the applied cathodic current density. Slightly lower HE rates were exhibited by the HP Mg when 1, 5 and 10 mA/cm² cathodic current densities were applied. The HE rate was slightly lower for the UHP Mg at the highest applied cathodic current density.

Over the whole range of anodic currents, the UHP Mg exhibited lower HE rates than the HP Mg. For the highest anodic currents densities applied (i.e. 10, 25 and 75 mA/cm²), the HE rate for the UHP Mg was about 10% lower than for the HP Mg. Larger differences were observed for the lowest anodic current densities and at the OCP where the HE rate was 40-60% lower for the UHP Mg.

The HE rate can be converted to a current density using Faraday's law. Fig. 5 shows the calculated current densities for the HE obtained during the galvanostatic experiments at different cathodic and anodic current densities, plotted against the measured potential. The results of duplicate experiments are plotted. Because of differences in the kinetics of the reactions for the two materials (as exemplified by the difference in OCP), the potentials were different for a given applied current density. The results for both materials are very similar to that reported previously [18]. The curves exhibit the characteristics of a typical polarization curve for a dissolving metal. However, the currents in this plot are associated with a cathodic reaction, HE, taking place across the full range of potential, both above and below the OCP. A representative potentiodynamic polarization curve for each material taken from Fig. 1 is included as a dashed line in Fig. 5 for comparative purposes. A very good correlation was observed, especially in the regions close to the OCP, where the potential drop caused by HE was minimized. However, it should be noted that the net current at potentials above the zero current potentials in the polarization curves were positive whereas the currents reported for the galvanostatic measurements were calculated from the HE at the working electrode.

Figs. 6 and 7 show the macroscopic appearances of the HP and the UHP Mg electrodes, respectively, after a net charge of 20 C was passed at different anodic current densities in 0.1 M NaCl solution. Figs. 6 and 7 also show higher magnification optical micrographs for the 1 and 75 mA/cm². The appearance of the two different purity Mg materials was similar, as both formed a filiform-like dark film. At 1 mA/cm², both Mg electrodes exhibited a surface that was partially covered with filiform tracks. As the anodic current density increased, the appearance changed even though the net charge passed remained constant: the filiform tracks covered more of the surface, gradually increasing the surface coverage of both Mg materials. For the highest current density of

75 mA/cm², the filiform tracks covered almost the entire electrode surface. The HP Mg exhibited a higher surface coverage of the dark corrosion product than the UHP Mg over the whole range of anodic current densities applied, especially in the low current density-regime. The major difference in the appearance of the surfaces of the two materials was observed for the lowest current density (i.e. 0.5 mA/cm²). Upon the application of this current, the HP Mg exhibited the same film formation pattern shown for higher polarizations, but with lower coverage of the dark corrosion product. However, at this low current density a different morphology in the corrosion attack was observed for the UHP Mg. No dark filiform corrosion product tracks were evident. Instead, the surface exhibited large pits that were covered with a white solid. Raman spectroscopy analysis of this precipitate (not shown) revealed that this product was Mg(OH)₂. This white corrosion product was observed on replicated experiments. When the white solid was removed from the surface with a cotton-tipped swab soaked in ethanol, a characteristic reflective metallic surface was revealed. Fig. 8 shows the surface appearance of the UHP Mg after a current density of 0.5 mA/cm² was applied in 0.1 M NaCl to a charge of 20 C, both before and after the white deposit was removed.

Fig. 9 shows the cross-section scanning electron micrographs for the HP and UHP Mg materials after an anodic current density of 75 mA/cm² was applied to a charge of 20 C. This current density value was selected for comparative purposes so that the dark corrosion product covered almost the entire surface for both Mg materials, as shown in Figs. 6 and 7. A very similar film thickness was exhibited, with comparable dome shaped protrusions formed into the metal corresponding to the dark filiform tracks.

3.3. Cathodic polarization experiments on corroded Mg surfaces

To evaluate the catalytic properties for the HE reaction of previously corroded specimens, potentiodynamic cathodic polarization measurements were performed using the approach taken by Birbilis et al. [20]. Fig. 10 shows cathodic potentiodynamic polarization curves for the HP and UHP Mg electrodes previously subjected to galvanostatic polarization at different anodic current densities to a charge of 20 C in 0.1 M NaCl solution. Electrolyte replacement was performed prior to the potentiodynamic polarization to avoid the influence on the cathodic electrode kinetics of any local pH change that might have occurred during the galvanostatic experiments. Representative results of replicated experiments are presented. Potentiodynamic cathodic polarization curves performed on HP and UHP Mg without any prior external charge application taken from Fig. 1 are also shown in Fig. 10 for comparative purposes. Both the HP and the UHP Mg exhibited increased cathodic current density after a galvanostatic anodic current was applied, which is in agreement with previous reports for HP Mg [22]. The HP Mg exhibited larger current density values than the UHP Mg over the whole range of potentials applied below the OCP after the galvanostatic treatment was performed, indicating that impurities affect the enhanced catalytic properties for the HE reaction.

For the HP Mg, the cathodic polarization curve after anodic polarization at the lowest current density value, 0.5 mA/cm^2 , resulted in the least increase over the unpolarized control sample. However, almost no difference in the polarization curves was observed for samples treated at the other current densities, from 5 to 75 mA/cm^2 . The UHP Mg mostly exhibited a similar behavior to the HP Mg as the cathodic current densities increased with an increase in the previously applied anodic current density. However, the behavior of the sample polarized after treatment at an anodic current density of 0.5 mA/cm^2 was significantly different. This sample, which is the one sample with white corrosion product film, exhibited the highest values of cathodic kinetics for the

treated UHP Mg samples. Furthermore, cathodic current density values were even higher than those exhibited by the HP Mg without any prior anodic treatment. This indicates a notable increase in the catalytic activity for HER of the UHP Mg surface upon the application of the lowest current density, and suggests that the dark corrosion product film is not a critical component in the enhancement.

4. DISCUSSION

The curves in Fig. 5 show a small difference between the anodic HE rates on HP and UHP Mg, but these curves contain large ohmic potential drops associated with the copious evolution of H₂ bubbles during the galvanostatic experiments, particularly at the highest current densities. To accurately evaluate the enhancement in the catalytic activity for HER of these surfaces, the ohmic drop must first be assessed and the electrode potentials corrected. The current interrupt method was used for measurement of potential during the galvanostatic experiments. Both the uncorrected and ohmic-corrected values of potential can be determined from the data acquisition software. The uncorrected values of potential at the end of the experiment were used for creating Fig 5. The results are replotted in Fig. 11 using the ohmic-corrected potentials at the end of each experiment, where a steady state potential was observed. The data exhibit a linear-like behavior in this semi-logarithmic plot for potentials both above and below the OCP. In the cathodic region, this behavior is consistent with an activation-controlled electrochemical reaction with kinetics given by the Tafel equation:

$$i_{HER} = i_{0,H,Mg} \exp\left(\frac{-(E - E_{rev,H})}{|b_c|}\right) \quad (7)$$

where i_{HER} is the current density associated with the HE reaction (A/cm^2), $i_{0,H,\text{Mg}}$ is the exchange current density for the evolution of H_2 on Mg (A/cm^2), E is the electrode potential, $E_{\text{rev,H}}$ is the reversible potential for the water reduction reaction, and $|b_c|$ is the absolute value of the cathodic Tafel slope. As mentioned, the currents associated with the HE reaction for the HP and UHP Mg followed the expected Tafel behavior defined by Eq. (7) when cathodic current densities were applied. The HE current densities when anodic currents were applied were much larger than those expected at the corresponding anodic potentials in the extrapolated cathodic Tafel lines (dashed lines in Fig. 11), which is the sign of a strong enhancement in the catalytic activity for the HER in the anodic region, even for the UHP Mg despite the reduction in the concentration of impurities. The maximum differences were found to occur when the highest anodic current densities were applied, where an enhancement of three orders of magnitude between the expected and the actual HE current values were exhibited by the two materials.

The Tafel slopes were determined from the linear fit of the cathodic Tafel lines, resulting in b_c values of -0.28 and -0.23 V/dec for the HP and the UHP Mg, respectively (see Fig. 11). Even though these values are lower than that estimated in a previous work for pure Mg under the same conditions (0.75 V/dec) [18], they are still higher than typical Tafel slopes reported for the HER on different metals, which are typically around -0.12 V/dec [26]. Differences in composition could result in different Tafel slopes. Nevertheless, given the high purity of both Mg electrodes, there is no basis to expect a difference. To allow comparison in further calculations, the Tafel slope was assumed identical for both materials and equal to -0.23 V/dec.

The catalytic ability for the HE reaction, assuming an activation-controlled kinetics, is embodied by the exchange current density for that reaction on a given material, which depends critically on the nature of the electrode. Of course, factors that change the composition of the

electrode surface, such as impurity enrichment, the formation of an oxide film and changes in the film composition can influence the exchange current density. It is possible to determine the values of $i_{0,H,Mg}$ by extrapolating the cathodic Tafel line to $E_{rev,H}$. The reversible potential for H₂ evolution depends on the solution pH, and not directly on the electrode nature, according to the Nernst equation, $E_{rev,H} = -0.059 pH$. As previously mentioned, the initial pH in the electrolyte (prior to the immersion of the electrode) was about 6. This deviation from the expected value of 7 was likely due to the presence of dissolved CO₂. Nevertheless, when Mg dissolves at the OCP, the pH value in the electrolyte has been reported to rapidly increase after immersion to a steady pH of about 11 in unbuffered neutral solution [27-29] or even higher (pH~12) [30]. This increase is due to the formation of hydroxyl ions as a result of Eq. (3) that are poorly compensated by the low rate of Mg ion hydrolysis. Thus, assuming that the pH = 11, $E_{rev,H} = -0.889 V_{SCE}$. The lowest dashed lines in Fig. 12 show the extrapolations of the results from the cathodic region (where no dark regions were observed on the electrode surface) to a potential of $-0.889 V_{SCE}$, resulting in $i_{0,H,Mg}$ values for the cathodic region of about 4×10^{-8} and 8×10^{-9} A/cm² for the HP and UHP Mg, respectively. This 5X increase in $i_{0,H,Mg}$ indicates a higher catalytic ability for the material with higher concentration of impurities, confirming that the catalytic activity for HE is dependent on surface impurities, even at very low concentrations. A larger difference would have been observed if the lines with different Tafel slope shown in Fig. 11 had been extrapolated to $E_{rev,H}$. It is worth noting that, even though the potentiodynamic polarization curves presented in Fig. 1 were not ohmic-corrected, a difference of one order of magnitude between the cathodic current densities obtained for the HP and UHP Mg electrodes was observed. Furthermore, considering the kinetics of the cathodic region for the plots in Fig. 1 in the potential range close to the OCP, where ohmic

effects were minimal, extrapolation to $E_{rev,H} = -0.889$ resulted in $i_{0,H,Mg}$ values of about 3×10^{-8} and 6×10^{-9} A/cm² for the HP and UHP Mg, respectively. These values were very similar to those obtained by the extrapolation of the calculated current densities for the HE obtained during the galvanostatic experiments at different cathodic current densities as a function of the ohmic-corrected potentials (see Fig. 12).

In the anodic region, both materials exhibited an increase in the HE current density with increasing measured voltage. This behavior is similar to that reported in a previous work [18]. As observed in Fig. 4, the HE rate for UHP Mg was lower than for the HP Mg over the whole range of anodic applied current density. However, Fig. 11 shows that the UHP Mg exhibited higher HE current densities than HP Mg in the anodic region at a given measured potential. Considering that the enhanced catalytic behavior for HE increases with potential above the OCP, and that those differences in the kinetics of the HE reaction in the cathodic region for the two materials resulted in a difference in OCP values, it is of interest to compare HE current density as a function of the overvoltage above their respective OCP values. As shown in Fig. 13, significantly higher HE current densities were measured on the HP Mg than on the UHP Mg over the whole range of anodic potentials. Differences increased with increasing anodic polarization, exhibiting the greatest difference at the highest applied anodic current densities even though the coverage by the dark corrosion product was similar for the HP and UHP Mg. This confirms the influence of the surface concentration of impurities on the HE rate during anodic polarization and supports the idea that the dark corrosion film plays a small role in the process.

Using the notion that the NDE results from a change in the catalytic activity as expressed by the exchange current density, it is possible to assess the apparent values of $i_{0,H,Mg}$ during anodic polarization by extrapolation of Tafel behavior to $E_{rev,H}$ as was done previously [18]. Fig. 12

contains a series of lines with slope -0.23 V/dec (using the Tafel slope in Fig. 11 for the UHP Mg for comparison) intersecting each of the current density points associated with HE during anodic polarization. The same value of $E_{rev,H} = -0.889$ V_{SCE} used above for the cathodic region extrapolation was used for the points in the anodic region. The local pH during anodic polarization is likely to be somewhat lower than in the cathodic region because of Mg²⁺ hydrolysis and the lower rate of HE. Attempts to measure the local pH near the electrode surface during dissolution were inconclusive, and the assumption of pH 11 allows for comparisons to be made.

Table 2 shows the $i_{0,H,Mg}$ values obtained by this procedure for the HP and UHP Mg subjected to the application of different anodic current densities and at the OCP in 0.1 M NaCl solution. The exchange current density exhibited a significant increase in both materials even for the lowest current imposed. The increment reached differences of 4 orders of magnitude when the highest current densities were applied for both materials, confirming a strong enhancement in the HE kinetics. The UHP Mg exhibited lower $i_{0,H,Mg}$ values over the whole range of currents imposed, about 20-40% of the values on HP Mg at similar values of applied current density. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that even for the UHP Mg, with a nominal purity of 99.9999%, a difference of four orders of magnitude exists between the HE exchange current density associated with the condition at the OCP and that associated with HE occurring during the largest anodic galvanostatic current. This indicates that, although the rate at which H₂ evolves from a dissolving Mg surface is influenced by the concentration of impurities, the enhancement in the HE rate under anodic polarization cannot be fully explained in terms of this consideration.

Another comparison of the effect of Mg purity on anodic HE is shown in Fig. 14 where the volume of H₂ normalized to the net charge is plotted as a function of applied current density. This is equivalent to the charge associated with HE normalized to the net charge applied, as shown

in the right-hand axis in Fig. 14. When cathodic currents were imposed, the hydrogen charge ratio was close to the expected value of 1, indicating that the collection efficiency was very good. Nevertheless, the HP Mg showed lower efficiencies than the UHP Mg over the whole range of cathodic currents applied, particularly for the lowest current densities (i.e. cathodic 1, 5 and 10 mA/cm²). This difference in the H₂ collection efficiencies might have been caused by differences in shape for the two Mg electrodes. The HP Mg electrode was square and the UHP electrode was circular. The evolved H₂ tended to accumulate at the interface between the metal and the resin. For the highest current densities applied (−25 and −75 mA/cm²), the copious generation of H₂ did not allow bubbles to settle down at this interface, resulting in very high collection efficiencies. However, for lower applied currents, where HE was less intense, bubbles did not readily leave the metal/resin interface. The larger exposed surface of the HP Mg electrode along with the difference in geometry with respect to the UHP Mg apparently resulted in a more extended interface and thus lower collection efficiencies. The limitations of this hydrogen collection set-up were recently reported by Kirkland et al. [30].

The amount of H₂ collected per unit of charge in the anodic region was less for both purities of Mg than in the cathodic region. The hydrogen volume or charge in the anodic region was very similar when anodic current densities of 10, 25 and 75 mA/cm² were applied, with values for the HE charge of about the 50% of the applied anodic charge. However, slightly higher values were observed for the HP Mg than for the UHP Mg. Williams et al. [21] used in-situ scanning vibrating electrode technique (SVET) to characterize the local current density distribution over high purity Mg surfaces subjected to dissolution under different anodic current density values in 2 M NaCl solution. They found that the mean cathodic current density appeared to remain substantially unaffected by the magnitude of the applied anodic current (i.e. 0.4, 1 and 2 mA/cm²). The net

charge passed was not fixed but analysis of the data indicates that the charge associated with the HE was in the range of 40-50% of the applied anodic charge, which is consistent with the findings in the present paper. It should be noted that the results at the anodic current density of 75 mA/cm² are different than what was presented previously [18] under similar conditions using the same HP Mg. In that work, H₂ gas evolving from the Mg surface was collected during the application of a net anodic charge of 50 C passed using different current densities. The amount of H₂ collected per unit of charge in the anodic region for HP Mg was about 50% of the applied anodic charge for current densities between 1 and 50 mA/cm², similar to what was observed in the present paper. However, at an anodic current density of 75 mA/cm², the amount of H₂ collected per unit of charge decreased to about 20% of the applied anodic charge whereas it remained similar to results exhibited for lower currents in the present investigation.

The fact that during anodic polarization a certain amount of the applied anodic charge was associated with HE indicates that, during the Mg dissolution process, some of the electrons generated by the Mg oxidation reaction (Eq. (1)) did not flow through the potentiostat to the counter electrode but rather were consumed by the HER on the Mg electrode surface. Therefore, the net anodic charge applied, Q_{net} , was less than the anodic charge associated with Mg oxidation, Q_{Mg} , by an amount equal to the cathodic charge associated with the HER, Q_{H_2} . Furthermore, in previous works [16, 31] it was shown that the formation of an insoluble Mg²⁺ product, likely the dark surface film, is associated with a consumption of some of the oxidation charge by an amount equal to Q_{film} :

$$Q_{net} = Q_{Mg} - Q_{H_2} - Q_{film} \quad (8)$$

Under anodic polarization, impurities are expected to progressively accumulate in or under the dark film formed on the electrode surface [1, 17, 22]. For high anodic current densities, both

Mg materials exhibited very a similar behavior with HE charge values of about 50% of the applied anodic charge. However, the HP Mg exhibited slightly higher hydrogen volumes than the UHP Mg. The HE volumes for UHP Mg were significantly lower than for HP Mg at low anodic current densities, and the difference increased with decreasing anodic current density. A significant increase in the HE volume was exhibited by the HP Mg with decreasing anodic current density, whereas the UHP Mg exhibited a slightly decreasing trend in the same range. Considering these results, it is interesting to note that, although the HE rates for both Mg purities were shown to decrease with decreasing anodic current density, implicitly meaning that catalytic activity for the HER of these surfaces became lower as the applied anodic current decreased (as embodied by the differences in $i_{0,H,Mg}$ shown in Table 2), the HE volume remained almost equal (UHP Mg) or increased significantly (HP Mg) with respect to those collected at higher currents. The fact that the HE charge is greater for a fixed anodic charge when the applied current density is low was pointed out recently by Thomas et al. [1] as one the topics of current interest not fully understood in the Mg corrosion field. They hypothesized that an increased local surface pH due to the longer times of application of the anodic charge (i.e. lower current density) may lead to a greater extent in the production of insoluble $Mg(OH)_2$. However, this would imply that a higher surface coverage should be expected at low current density. Figs. 6 and 7 show that there was lower surface coverage of dark corrosion product for the lowest current densities applied, which contradicts the previous hypothesis.

The HP Mg exhibited higher HE rates than the UHP Mg over the whole range of anodic currents applied (see Fig. 4). Differences between them increased as the applied anodic current decreased. The trend was reversed when the rate was plotted against the ohmic-corrected measured potential because of a difference in the OCP for the two materials (Fig. 11), but the HE rate was

shown to be much higher on HP Mg for a given overpotential from each material's OCP (Fig. 13). The controlling factor in the HE rate is therefore the rate of dissolution, not the potential.

The copious HE that accompanies Mg dissolution along with the weak hydrolysis of the Mg^{2+} ion results in alkalization of the nearby solution. This local increase in pH favors the precipitation of Mg^{2+} in the form of $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$. The extent of the precipitation of the corrosion product will depend directly on the extent of pH increase. The higher rate of HE occurring with increased applied anodic current density results in a higher increase in pH and thus more corrosion product, as shown in Fig. 6. Similarly, the higher rate of HE accompanying dissolution of HP Mg than UHP Mg results in a higher increase in pH and thus more corrosion product, as shown by the comparison between Figs. 6 and 7. The higher cathodic currents measured on samples previously polarized anodically (Fig. 10) suggests that the corrosion product or impurities accumulated in or under it can play a role in the enhanced catalytic nature of the surface during anodic dissolution. However, the properties of the corrosion film cannot explain all of the observations. For example, the HE rate is constant for a fixed anodic current density even though the corrosion film accumulates with the time of experimentation, both at the OCP and upon anodic polarization. Consequently, it seems appropriate to reconsider the role of the dark corrosion film to successfully explain the enhanced catalytic activity for HER of dissolving Mg.

It is reasonable to assume that the corrosion film and the accumulated impurities are robust in that they are relatively unchanged during subsequent cathodic polarization. As a result, their influence during anodic polarization can be assessed by extrapolation of the behavior in the cathodic region to the potentials reached during anodic polarization. Fig. 15a shows the HE rates associated with the corrosion film and the accumulated impurities in or under the corrosion film on HP and UHP Mg during anodic polarization as a function of the applied anodic current density.

These values were obtained by polarizing the samples at different current densities to a charge of 20 C, subsequently measuring cathodic polarization curves on those samples, and extrapolating the cathodic curves to the IR-corrected potentials measured during the anodic polarization. Because of curvature in the curves associated with IR drop, the cathodic Tafel slope for all samples was assumed -0.23 V/dec. This is the value previously determined for the UHP Mg by the linear fit of the cathodic Tafel line obtained from the current density associated with HE vs. the ohmic-corrected potential (see Fig. 11). The assumption of this Tafel slope allows for straightforward comparisons. The same procedure was carried out for the samples in the absence of any prior anodic treatment and results are presented as dashed lines in Fig. 15a for comparative purposes. For the UHP Mg, the HE rate during anodic polarization associated with the corrosion film and the accumulated noble impurities was relatively independent of the applied potential and similar to the value for the sample with no pre-polarization. The sample subjected to an anodic current density of 0.5 mA/cm² behaved differently as the cathodic current on this sample was much larger, as shown in Fig. 10. This was the condition with corrosion product that was white instead of dark. Davidge [32] reported that MgO doped with Fe looks dark in appearance so it is possible that less impurity is accumulated within the corrosion product on UHP Mg at the low current density of 0.5 mA/cm² and that this white product has different properties. No surface analysis was performed, but if this analysis is correct, then accumulation of impurities in the corrosion product actually hinders the HE process. This would indicate that impurities under the corrosion product, not within it, create the condition for enhanced cathodic reactivity.

For the HP Mg, the rates of HE associated with the corrosion film and accumulated impurity during anodic polarization were almost 10X higher than that for a sample with no prior polarization, which is consistent with the idea of noble impurity enrichment in or under the dark

corrosion film. As pointed out by Cain et al. [17], there is no reason to expect that noble impurities captured in the poorly conductive Mg oxide/hydroxide corrosion film during dissolution should contribute to a large extent to anodic HE. Therefore, it seems that impurities accumulated on the electrode surface under the dark corrosion film were responsible for this behavior in the anodic region as well as the higher current density under cathodic polarization. Furthermore, there was almost no variation in the HE rate associated with the dark corrosion product and the impurity enriched surface during anodic polarization even though the corrosion film coverage increased with increasing applied anodic current density. This further supports the notion that the dark corrosion product is not responsible for causing the enhancement of anodic HE.

The difference between the total HE rate measured during anodic polarization and the HE rates determined to come from the accumulated noble impurities presented (shown in Fig. 15a) must be the HE rate associated with the regions dominated by the anodic dissolution reaction. The symbols in Fig. 15b represent these values of HE coming from the anodic dissolution regions and the dashed lines in Fig. 15 b represent the total HE rates measured during anodic polarization (referred to as “global”). The HE rate associated with the accumulated noble element impurities is small compared to the HE rate associated with the anodic regions, which is almost equal to the total rate of HE. The largest effect of the accumulated impurities was found at the lowest applied anodic current densities. However, the very high HE rates observed during anodic dissolution of Mg (the NDE) therefore are primarily associated with the regions dominated by the anodic dissolution reaction.

It should be noted that the cathodic currents measured on the pre-polarized samples in Fig. 10 include current associate with the unfilmed areas that had not experienced anodic attack and were therefore probably not enriched in impurities. Therefore, the extrapolation of these curves to

the anodic potentials provides an overestimate of the HE associated with the impurity enriched regions.

The enhanced catalytic nature of the dissolving surface will depend upon the details of the surface, including the rate of dissolution. The component of the HE rate associated with the anodic region increases strongly with applied anodic current density. Furthermore, this component is larger for HP than for UHP Mg, suggesting that impurity enrichment on the anodically dissolving surface enhances this catalytic nature. However, the effect of impurities is small. It is certainly possible that the very low level of impurities in UHP Mg plays a role in this enhancement. Nonetheless, the behavior of UHP Mg of 99.9999% purity represents that of pure Mg as much as is possible and the dissolving Mg surface is seen to be extremely catalytic to HE, resulting in very large rates of HE during dissolution.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Galvanostatic measurements coupled with H₂ collection and potentiodynamic polarization experiments were carried out on high purity (99.98% Mg) and ultra-high purity Mg (99.9999% Mg) electrodes to determine the effect of impurities on the H₂ evolution kinetics upon cathodic and anodic polarization. The following can be concluded:

- Even at low levels, the concentration of impurities in Mg influences the kinetics of the hydrogen evolution reaction in the cathodic region on a freshly prepared surface and on a previously-dissolved surface, as well as during anodic polarization.
- The HE rate during anodic polarization is lower for UHP Mg than for HP Mg for all values of applied anodic current density and overpotential from the OCP, which is different for the two materials.

- The enhanced catalytic activity for HER was quantified by comparing estimated values of the exchange current density for the hydrogen evolution reaction during anodic polarization.
- The dark corrosion product film formed during dissolution appeared not to play a role in the enhanced HE rates during anodic polarization.
- Increased concentration of impurities accumulated under the dark corrosion product film increased the HE rate during anodic polarization. However, extrapolation of the behavior in the cathodic region to the anodic potentials proved that the HE rate associated with the accumulated products was small during anodic polarization.
- The enhancement in the catalytic activity for HER on dissolving Mg surfaces is primarily associated with the regions dominated by the anodic dissolution reaction. Increased concentration of impurities in Mg increases the HE rate at this anodic regions, especially at low anodic current density values, but this effect of impurities is small as the rate on the UHP Mg was extremely high.

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Fig. 1. Potentiodynamic polarization curves for the HP and UHP Mg electrodes in 0.1 M NaCl solution. Experiments performed in a single scan upwards starting from the cathodic region at a scan rate of 1 mV/s.

Fig. 2. Volume of hydrogen collected as a function of time for the HP Mg electrode in 0.1 M NaCl during the application of different (a) anodic and (b) cathodic current densities. Typical data from replicated experiments are presented. A net charge of 20 C was passed.

Fig. 3. Volume of hydrogen collected as a function of time for the UHP Mg electrode in 0.1 M NaCl during the application of different (a) anodic and (b) cathodic current densities. Typical data from replicated experiments are presented. A net charge of 20 C was passed.

Fig. 4. Rate of hydrogen evolution on the HP and UHP Mg electrodes as a function of the applied current density in 0.1 M NaCl solution. Data of duplicated experiments are presented. A net charge of 20 C was passed.

Fig. 5. Current density associated with HE for the HP and UHP Mg electrodes in 0.1 M NaCl solution as a function of the measured potential. Current density values were calculated from the HE rates during galvanostatic polarization measurements and potentials are steady state values not corrected for ohmic potential drop. The net charge passed was 20 C. Dashed lines are typical potentiodynamic polarization curves for the HP and UHP Mg in 0.1 M NaCl, taken from Fig. 1.

Fig. 6. Surface appearance and optical micrographs of the HP Mg electrode after the application of different anodic current densities in 0.1 M NaCl solution. The net charge passed was 20 C.

Fig. 7. Surface appearance and optical micrographs of the UHP Mg electrode after the application of different anodic current densities in 0.1 M NaCl solution. The net charge passed was 20 C.

Fig. 8. Surface appearance of the UHP Mg electrode after an anodic current density application of 0.5 mA/cm^2 in 0.1 M NaCl solution. The net charge passed was 20 C .

Fig. 9. Scanning electron micrographs of the HP and UHP Mg electrodes after an anodic current density application of 75 mA/cm^2 in 0.1 M NaCl solution. The net charge passed was 20 C .

Fig. 10. Cathodic potentiodynamic polarization curves for the HP and UHP Mg electrodes in 0.1 M NaCl solution after galvanostatic polarization at different anodic current densities. The net charge passed in the galvanostatic treatment was 20 C. Experiments were performed in a single scan downwards starting from the OCP. A potential scan rate of 1 mV/s was used. Typical potentiodynamic polarization curves for the HP and UHP Mg in 0.1 M NaCl, taken from Fig. 1, are plotted for comparative purposes.

Fig. 11. Current density associated with HE for the HP and UHP Mg electrodes in 0.1 M NaCl solution as a function of the ohmic-corrected steady-state potential. Current density values were calculated from the HE rates during galvanostatic polarization measurements. Ohmic potential drop correction was achieved by current interrupt measurements during the galvanostatic tests. The net charge passed was 20 C. Solid lines are cathodic Tafel slopes determined from the linear fit of the data.

Fig. 12. Overlay of Tafel slopes ($b_c = -0.23 \text{ V/dec}$) onto data taken from Fig. 11 to a reversible potential of $-0.889 \text{ V}_{\text{SCE}}$ (pH=11) to determine the exchange current density for HER on the HP and UHP Mg electrodes in 0.1 M NaCl solution.

Fig. 13. Current density associated with HE for the HP and UHP Mg electrodes in 0.1 M NaCl solution as a function of the overvoltage above their respective E_{corr} values. Current density values were calculated from the HE rates during galvanostatic polarization measurements. Potentials are ohmic-corrected steady-state values. The net charge passed was 20 C.

Fig. 14. Volume of hydrogen produced normalized to the net charge for the HP and UHP Mg electrodes in 0.1 M NaCl solution. Right hand axis shows the charge associated with the hydrogen production normalized to the net charge. The net charge passed was 20 C. The dashed line is given to facilitate comparison with a charge ratio of 1.

Fig. 15. Hydrogen evolution rate associated with a) the corrosion product and accumulation of noble impurities, and b) the dissolving anodic sites for the HP and UHP Mg electrodes in 0.1 M NaCl solution. The net charge passed was 20 C.

Table 1. Chemical composition of the high purity (HP) and ultra-high purity (UHP) Mg used.

All compositions reported in parts per million (ppm) by weight. The balance was Mg.

Material	Al	Zn	Mn	Fe	Cu	Ni	Si
HP Mg	100	<100	100	40	20	<10	100
UHP Mg	0.3	0.2	<0.05	0.1	<0.05	<0.05	0.1

Table 2. Calculated exchange current density values for the HP and UHP Mg electrodes at the OCP and under anodic galvanostatic polarization in 0.1 M NaCl solution. The net charge passed was 20 C.

Applied current density (mA/cm ²)	Exchange current density, $i_{0,H,Mg}$ (A/cm ²)	
	HP Mg	UHP Mg
OCP	4×10^{-8}	8×10^{-9}
0.5	4×10^{-7}	6×10^{-8}
1	9×10^{-7}	2×10^{-7}
5	5×10^{-6}	1×10^{-6}
10	9×10^{-6}	3×10^{-6}
25	3×10^{-5}	1×10^{-5}
75	1×10^{-4}	4×10^{-5}